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Rethinking Hybrid and Remote Work in Higher Education

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“Rethinking Hybrid and Remote Work in Higher Education” brings together scholarship from diverse regions including North America, South America, Africa, Southeast Asia, and East Asia, presenting varied perspectives on crucial issues in global higher education. The book is structured into three sections and seventeen chapters, focusing on opportunities and challenges, perceptions, policies, practices, and case studies related to hybrid and remote work in academia. This review will examine the prologue, sections one through three, and the conclusion.

The prologue initiates with a focus on the global impact of the Covid-19 pandemic, particularly within higher education. The first section shed light on the realistic possibilities and obstacles of hybrid and remote work in global higher education post-pandemic, advocating for organizational commitment to diversity, equity, and inclusion. Topics covered include faculty fatigue, 'quiet quitting,' and employment law. It also explores challenges and solutions faced by student affairs practitioners and examines the role of faculty development in enhancing faculty sense of belonging and support for online teaching. The section concludes with insights for universities aiming to ensure quality remote and in-person instruction, drawing on experiences from educators in the U.S. and China.

Section two highlights best practices for global online learning. It discusses faculty perceptions of online and hybrid teaching in Indonesia and showcases how the Chinese Flagship program influenced a blended learning model at Indiana University. Additionally, the section examines student perspectives on flexible learning environments and offers recommendations for practitioners. It also explores how online learning fosters self-directed learning skills in Hong Kong. The final chapter of this section addresses the gendered impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the academic workforce, emphasizing structural inequalities.

The third section presents case studies and lessons learned on hybrid and remote work from various countries, including South Africa, Nepal, Egypt, Peru, and Vietnam. The book concludes by offering insights tailored for educators, administrators, practitioners, policymakers, and families. "Rethinking Hybrid and Remote Work in Higher Education" is a well-timed resource that offers comprehensive insights, sound scholarship, and innovative guidance, playing a pivotal role in shaping future discourse regarding cross national and cross-cultural perspectives on hybrid and remote work in higher education.

Reference

Chan, R., Lin, X., & Bista, K. (2023) *Rethinking Hybrid and Remote Work in Higher Education*. Palgrave.

About the Reviewer

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